

Bridging the Gap: Increasing Evidence-Based Practice Utilization Among Experienced Nurses

Sandy Hall, DNP, MBA, RN-BC, NE-BC; Kathleen Hinoki, PhD, MSN, RN, CNS; Jean O'Neil, DNP, RN, FNP-BC

Background

- Evidence-based practice (EBP) is a core competency for health care professionals. (Institute of Medicine, 2003)
- Evidence suggests that time from research publication to adoption into practice takes roughly 17 years. (Balas & Boren, 2000)
- Knowledge deficit has been identified as the most prevalent barrier to nurse utilization of EBP. (Pravlikoff, Tanner, & Pierce, 2005)
- Leaders at Children's Hospital Los Angeles (CHLA) are working to create a culture of inquiry among nursing staff.
- Currently no formalized ongoing education exists to provide experienced nurses with EBP knowledge and skills.

Purpose

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to develop a one-year EBP Fellowship Program for nurses at CHLA.

Methods

- Search literature for evidence related to the following topics:
 - Significance and benefits of EBP
 - Barriers to EBP utilization among nurses
 - Facilitators for EBP utilization among nurses
 - Methods of EBP education
 - Examples of EBP fellowship programs
 - Measurement of EBP outcomes
- Appraise and synthesize literature to identify evidence-based structure for EBP Fellowship Program
- Obtain IRB non-research waiver through CHLA and California State University, Los Angeles
- Develop EBP Fellowship Program curriculum and outcomes
- Identify logistical procedures for program, including program guidelines, budget, and participant application and selection procedures
- Collaborate with CHLA's Clinical Services Research Council, Institute for Nursing and Interprofessional Research, and Quality Improvement team for program development and support
- Identify program outcomes and obtain permission to use validated instruments

Conceptual Framework

- Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice Model
- PET (Practice Question, Evidence, Translation) process utilized to appraise and synthesize evidence in development of EBP Fellowship Program
- Model additionally utilized as framework for program curriculum

Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice PET Process

Implementation Timeline

- Anticipated launch in September 2019 (pending program funding)
- Program announcements to staff in May 2019
- Applications open in June 2019
- Selected participants to be notified by August 1, 2019

Outcome Measures

- Evidence-Based Practice Self-Efficacy Scale (EBPSE):
 - Measures participant's confidence in utilizing EBP
 - To be assessed pre- and post-program participation
- Evidence-Based Practice Knowledge Assessment for Nurses (EKAN):
 - Measures objective EBP knowledge
 - To be assessed pre- and post-program participation
- Number of nursing EBP projects completed annually at CHLA to be monitored for anticipated increase

Results

Program Components Developed

- Program curriculum
- Program outcomes
- Program application
- Application scoring rubric
- Program participant guidelines
- Participant project progress report
- Program budget

The form is titled 'EBP Fellowship Application' and includes fields for Name, Email, Department, and Manager's Name. It contains several sections for the applicant to provide information, including a 'Please indicate the following items' section with checkboxes for 'Signed application' and 'Short (200 words or less) essay about your type of interest, population affected, and potential impact of your project'.

The rubric is titled 'EBP Fellowship Application Scoring Rubric' and lists various criteria for evaluation, such as 'Potential Impact', 'Feasibility', 'Applicant's Research', and 'Program Completion'. Each criterion has a corresponding score range from 0 to 5.

The curriculum form is titled 'Evidence-Based Practice Fellowship Curriculum' and includes a table with columns for 'Unit Name', 'Description', and 'Hours'. It details the structure of the fellowship program, including topics like 'Introduction to Evidence-Based Practice' and 'Evidence Synthesis'.

Challenges

- Difficulty obtaining funding for program forced delay in program implementation
- Creating a justification for staffing increase to compensate for nurse time away from clinical work

Discussion/Implications

- Nurse utilization of EBP has the potential to improve patient outcomes and reduce health care savings
- Engagement in EBP can improve nurses' sense of autonomy and satisfaction, ultimately resulting in increased nurse retention
- Organizational support for EBP education is crucial to ensuring advancement of nursing workforce and provision of high quality patient care
- Leaders must identify methods of fostering acquisition of EBP knowledge and skill
- Implementation of EBP Fellowship Program will help to develop a culture of inquiry
- Program must include provision of protected time to engage in the work of EBP

Program Highlights

- Initial cohort of 8 participants to be selected
- Applications to be reviewed and scored by members of Clinical Services Research Council
- Participants will attend one 6-hour class each month
- Participants will have an additional 6 hours of paid time to work on project each month
- Each participant to be paired with EBP mentor
- Participants will engage in experiential learning through conduction of EBP projects
- Following evidence synthesis, participants may proceed with EBP intervention translation, research study, or quality improvement project as appropriate based on existing evidence